

MÖBIUS

D5.3 Möbius open piloting

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Executive Summary

The Möbius Project, funded by the European Commission Horizon 2020 Programme, seeks to revitalize the traditional European book publishing sector by introducing innovative technological tools. These tools aim to enhance media experiences, revealing the prosumer's potential as valuable contributors and ultimate drivers in implementing and designing new products and services that align with Möbius' objectives. This initiative aligns with the broader goal of embracing digital transformation across various sectors, as advocated by the European Union. In addition, Möbius aims to reshape the current traditional publishing landscape, fostering a symbiotic relationship between publishers and prosumers while delivering cutting-edge, immersive book experiences.

Deliverable 5.3 *Möbius Open Piloting* offers a comprehensive overview detailing all open pilot activities and events executed during Pilot Phase 3 Open Pilot and Experimental Productions by Möbius project partners. Serving as a continuation of preceding piloting endeavours, this phase represents a crucial stage in engaging users for testing and evaluating Möbius outputs across diverse settings.

The Piloting process is focused on three Pilot Phases:

- Pilot Phase 1, running from Month 9 to 12 focused on concept formulation and prototype developments.
- Pilot Phase 2, spanning from Months 13 to 18, centred on refining prototypes and conducting evaluations.
- Pilot Phase 3, stretched from Months 20 to 36, marking a significant shift towards involving users in testing Möbius innovations.

Among the innovations developed by the Möbius project is Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT), designed as an online application to facilitate learning from open communities and understanding global reader bases (accessible at <https://mobius-pit.in-two.com/>). Another innovation is the Möbius Book, incorporating the Player (<https://mobius-player.in-two.com/>) and the Creator software tools (<https://mobius-creator.in-two.com/login>), aimed at delivering immersive and interactive book experiences tailored for both readers and writers. In addition to these innovations which were tested already during Pilot Phases 1 and 3, Pilot Phase 3 saw the emergence of experimental productions, including the Mobile Immersive Book Box (MIBB), Virtual Reality (VR) Headsets, and an Immersive Art Installation hosted in Leipzig, Germany (<https://mobius-project.eu/mobius-book-experience/>). These productions sought to push the boundaries of immersive storytelling, offering users novel experiences within the book consumption ecosystem.

Stakeholder engagement was a cornerstone of the piloting process, with partners actively involving stakeholders from various European countries, namely Austria, Belgium, Finland, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, and the United Kingdom. These stakeholders included authors, readers and professionals working in the publishing industry. Möbius made appearances at key industry events, notably book fairs, leveraging these

platforms to showcase project tools and engage appropriate testers. All in all, the Möbius outputs were piloted at 29 different digital or in-person events. At these events, the General User Evaluation Survey was conducted. This is divided into two types of surveys: the User Requirement Survey and the Assessment Survey.

Figure 1 below shows the number of responses recorded for the User Requirement Survey for different products.

Figure 1

A User Requirement Survey was not conducted for the VR Headsets, the Mobile Immersive Book Box or the Immersive Experience. With regards to the users reached for the Impact Assessment survey, these numbers are significantly lower, since the survey was deployed in the later stage of the Pilot Phase 3 with the goal of assessing the impact of the final products. The numbers of participants are showcased in

Figure 2.

Figure 2. Participation in Impact Assessment survey

It should be noted that, while only 56 surveys were conducted for the Mobile Immersive Book Box, we estimate that it attracted a broader public, with a total of about 738-948 visitors.

Throughout the piloting period, various challenges were recorded, including low response rates for PIT interviews, difficulties in understanding PIT data accessibility, and perceived lack of differentiation in existing applications. Technical challenges, audience preferences, and language barriers further compounded these challenges, underscoring the complexity of the piloting process.

While a total of 3 responses for the PIT were collected through the Impact Assessment survey, it is important to underline that all KPIs initially established were reached and exceeded, with a total of 171 responses for the Möbius Player, 111 responses for the Möbius Creator, 112 responses for the VR headsets, and 56 responses for the Mobile Immersive Book Box.

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Partner Names

EUT	Fundacio Eurecat
IMEC	Interuniversitair Micro- Electronica Centrum
DEN	Design Entrepreneurship Institute
IN2	In2 Digital Innovations GmbH
MVB	Mvb Marketing Und Verlagsservice Des Buchhandels GmbH
BookaBook	Bookabook Srl
ENoLL	European Network Of Living Labs Ivzw
FMWC	Fundació Mobile World Capital Barcelona
FEP	Federation Des Editeurs Europeens
KKW	Kunstkraftwerk Leipzig GmbH
KU LEUVEN	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven
LAUREA	Laurea University Of Applied Sciences
KPT	Krakowski Park Technologiczny

Terminology and Acronyms

D	Deliverable
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FP	Framework Programme
PMB	Project Management Board
PMP	Project Management Plan
WP	Work Package
PIT	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit
VR	Virtual Reality
MIBB	Mobile Immersive Book Box
WP	Work Package
PAN e. V.	Phantastik-Autoren-Netzwerk (PAN) e. V.

1. Introduction

The Möbius Project seeks to revitalize the traditional European book publishing sector by introducing innovative technological tools and reshape the current traditional publishing landscape, fostering a symbiotic relationship between publishers and prosumers while delivering cutting-edge, immersive book experiences. For this reason, Möbius developed the Möbius Innovations, and the Experimental Productions, shown in Figure 3.

Möbius Innovations are:

- The **Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT)**, an online application through which users can learn from the most prolific open communities to better understand global readers' base.
- **Prosumer Business Model**, as Möbius has set to design a new business model archetypes grounded in IPR and copyright law for fair attribution and retributions.
- **The Möbius Book**, which combines two software tools that will allow the production of new immersive and interactive book experiences. These are the Player and the Creator. The Player is aimed at readers seeking an interactive and immersive experience, while the Creator targets writers and allows the production of 3D audio and cross-media experiences linked to the book.

The Möbius innovations can be accessed at <https://mobius-project.eu/products/>.

In addition, the Möbius Book also falls under the **experimental productions** alongside:

- The **Mobile Immersive Book Box (MIBB)**, a transportable 5m x 5m x 3m audio-visual space, allowing an immersive experience of the contents of a book.
- The **Virtual Reality (VR) Headsets**, which showcase the same experience as the MIBB, adapted to the VR headsets to allow a user to experience an immersive show without the need for any physical installation.
- The **Immersive Experience** in the form of an art installation hosted in Leipzig, Germany at the KKW premises. The installation includes digital animation, 2D and 3D characters, visual effects, 3D models, compositing, motion graphics, arranged with music and special 3D spatial sound effects.

The experimental productions showcase excerpts of two books; The "*Influence of blue*", selected by Bookabook, and "*Fantasy into Möbius*", which was selected as the winning manuscript. The experimental products and the books can be accessed at <https://mobius-project.eu/mobius-book-experience/>.

Figure 3. Möbius Experimental Productions

The Möbius Innovations and Experimental productions have been developed with and/or tested by end-users through three pilot phases, graphically showcased in Figure 3. These phases are:

- **Pilot Phase 1: Concept and prototype development.** Set to run from M9-M12, this pilot phase aimed at co-creating ideas on the first prototype together with the different user groups and tested in a controlled setting. In this phase, the piloting focused on the Möbius Player, Creator and the PIT and was conducted online due to the Covid-19 pandemic related lockdowns and gathering restrictions. The concept and prototype development took place between January and March 2022 and a total of 60-70 end-users were involved. The results from Pilot Phase 1 are reported in Deliverable 2.3 *Möbius evaluation framework and large scale pilot descriptions* (accessible at <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/957185/results>) and D2.4 *Möbius value proposition: an evaluation*.
- **Pilot Phase 2: Prototype refinement and evaluation.** Pilot Phase 2, scheduled to run from M13 to M18, focused on the refinement and evaluation of the first prototypes of the Möbius Player, Creator and the PIT. At this stage a total of 360 individuals were targeted in face-to-face sessions held in Belgium, Spain, Italy, and Germany. The geographical outreach was extended to include Poland and Finland. The timeline for Pilot Phase 2 was extended until M19 (October 2022), as the first prototypes were developed during the summer period when reaching testers proved challenging. The outcomes of Pilot Phase 2 are detailed in D2.3 *Möbius evaluation framework and large-scale pilot descriptions* and D2.4 *Möbius value proposition: an evaluation*.
- **Pilot phase 3: Open pilot and experimental productions.** Pilot Phase 3, spanning M20 to M36, marked the conclusive stage involving users in the testing and evaluation of Möbius outputs across diverse settings. These settings ranged from participants' natural environments, where they typically engage with books or use the Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit, to public events such as book fairs and art exhibitions. Möbius was set to orchestrate 15 open test and validation events, and the number was reached and surpassed, as 29 different piloting events were held online or in-person. Feedback was collected through various methods, including observation, in-depth interviews, and online surveys conducted via an online platform Hotjar that was directly embedded to the websites. Hotjar did not work properly, as in most cases only a section of the questions were answered. For that reason, the approach was modified at the beginning of Pilot Phase 3a to ensure proper collection of data in terms of quantity and quality. Consequently, the data collected through Hotjar were used to support data from the

other surveys but will not count in the total of responses collected per survey. For the Pilot Phase 3, we estimated the participation of over 600 users who would answer the surveys, with a minimum of 100 per pilot location.

This deliverable exclusively focuses on the events and piloting activities carried out during Pilot Phase 3. These activities were conducted within WP5 *Möbius experimental productions*, specifically under task T5.3 *Open tests and validation*. The primary objective of this task is to test and assess the Möbius Book Experiences through user engagement activities in alignment with the goals of Pilot Phase 3.

Figure 4. Pilot Phases and targets

Pilot Phase 3, is further divided into Pilot Phase 3a and 3b, as demonstrated in Figure 4. Pilot Phase 3a, consists of collecting data on the user requirement and impact assessment of the Möbius book and PIT, while Phase 3b mostly consists of demonstration of the Möbius experiences at different events, since the development process was already finalised. The target number of individuals at demonstration events is 2500.

The Möbius consortium comprises 11 partners from four European countries - Belgium, Germany, Italy, and Spain. Initially, Pilot Phase 1 testing took place in these countries and expanded in subsequent phases. With the activation of ENoLL's Living Labs network, piloting activities for Phases 2 and 3 extended to include Poland and Finland, introducing two new geographical areas. Furthermore, testing for Pilot Phase 3 was conducted in four additional countries: Austria, Slovenia, the UK, and the Netherlands. The geographical coverage of Pilot Phase 3 is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Geographical outreach of Pilot Phase 3

This deliverable follows a structure based on the geographical outreach of the piloting activities, incorporating reports from various countries where the outputs underwent testing. In Chapter 1, the Piloting activity is introduced, and the involvement of each partner in the Open Pilots is detailed. Chapter 2 provides additional details on the Piloting events, organized by country, including Belgium, Spain, Italy, Germany, Finland, Poland, and other countries classified as "other," namely Austria, Slovenia, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom. This chapter also includes insights from online events. Following this, Chapter 3 presents recommendations and lessons learned from the piloting activities.

1.1 Contribution of Partners

The *Open Tests and Validations* task witnessed a high level of collaboration, with active participation from all consortium partners and affiliated entities. This section highlights the specific activities conducted by the partners during this collaborative effort.

As the leader of the task, **ENoLL** coordinated the activities closely with IMEC and expanded the geographical outreach of the project, by engaging two Living Labs from the network

following an internal Open Call - Laurea **University of Applied Sciences (LAUREA)** from Finland, and **Krakowski Park Technologiczny (KPT)** from Poland. The two Living Labs led different open pilot activities within their home countries, ensuring a larger coverage and additional testers outside the consortium partners' countries area,

ENoLL played a leading role in various onsite and online piloting activities. Table 1 showcases all events in which ENoLL directly participated as the organizer.

Location, Country	Date	Name of the event	Type of event
London, UK	18-20 April 2023	London Book Fair	Onsite
Torino, Italy	18-22 May 2023	Salone Internazionale del Libro di Torino	Onsite
Barcelona, Spain	21-23 September 2023	OpenLivingLab Days 2023	Onsite
Madrid, Spain	3-6 October 2023	LIBER Madrid Book Fair	Onsite
Vienna, Austria	8-12 November 2023	Buch Wien - Vienna Book Fair	Onsite
Ljubljana, Slovenia	21-24 November 2023	Ljubljana knjižni sejem – Ljubljana Book Fair	Onsite
Mataró, Spain	5 December 2023	Mataró Libraries	Onsite
Italy	7-17 December 2023	Italy Piloting Activity with Targeted Stakeholders	Online
Brussels, Belgium	18-20 December 2023	Brussels piloting event with targeted stakeholders	Onsite

Table 1. List of events organised by ENoLL under Pilot Phase 3

In addition to this list of events, ENoLL also supported LAUREA and KPT in the facilitation of information for the organisation of workshops and events in their respective countries. The events organised by both organisations are presented in Chapter 2.

ENoLL actively engaged in weekly and bi-weekly meetings with fellow project partners, maintaining consistent coordination, particularly with IMEC and DEN. The primary objective

was to implement two distinct questionnaires—one User Requirement Survey with open-ended questions (devised by IMEC) and one Impact Assessment Survey with closed-ended questions (devised by DEN and IMEC). These surveys were designed to evaluate participants' experiences with the Möbius applications during pilot activities and events. ENoLL administered both types of surveys to diverse users during the events it participated in, providing regular updates to both IMEC and DEN regarding the collected data. Furthermore, to ensure an active, dynamic, and accurate promotion and dissemination of the Möbius project throughout the Möbius social media, ENoLL provided FMWC, the coordinator of WP6 on Communication and Dissemination, with photos and videos from the different event locations.

IMEC created a manual for Pilot phase 3 that served as a guide for all partners involved with the piloting. Together with ENoLL, an agreement was also accomplished on the number of participants to be reached in each country. The amount set was initially larger than what was stated in the proposal, to make sure we still had some room, if we could not reach enough participants in certain countries. In addition, IMEC prepared evaluation questionnaires on user experiences which were used during Pilot Phase 3a. Further information on the questionnaires is provided in Chapter 1.3 on Methodology.

As there were no events in Belgium, IMEC mainly contributed by participating to events abroad, where possible. These events included Readmagine Madrid (2023), the International Broadcasting Convention in Amsterdam (2023), the Frankfurt Bookfair (2023), and the Leipzig bookfair (2023). Furthermore, IMEC conducted various workshops and 1-to-1 interviews. These were based on the general questionnaire but were later transformed into a more interactive format. For all workshops and 1to1 interviews, participants were asked to complete the informed consent.

In addition, together with ENoLL, DEN and IN2, IMEC integrated Hotjar, an online data collection tool, into the data collection strategy. The goal was to allow piloting partners to get real-time feedback on the applications from respondents who were reached via mail, website, or social media. Nonetheless, the application did not produce the expected results, as the users did not answer all questions. During Pilot Phase 3b, IMEC assisted at events conducting surveys designed by DEN.

The **DEN Institute** led *WP2: Möbius framework and design principles*, and more specifically *Tasks 2.2 Evaluation framework and key performance indicators* and *2.4 Analysis of the results and validation of the methodology*, which entail the design and development of the criteria, the process and the tools that will be used to evaluate and measure the project activities, hypothesis, results and impact, and the analysis of the results and validation of the methodology. Following the establishment of the methodology already presented in *D2.3 Möbius evaluation framework and large-scale pilot descriptions*, DEN's responsibility has been to guide partners in the impact assessment activities for Pilot Phase 3. DEN also actively participated in the piloting activities, especially in Pilot Phase 3 (IBC Amsterdam 2023, Frankfurter Buchmesse 2023, MWC Barcelona 2024) Further information on the impact assessment methodology developed by DEN can be found in Chapter 1.3 on Methodology and approach.

Due to its connection with the Frankfurter Buchmesse, **MVB** oversaw setting up the space for the piloting activities planned during the 75th Frankfurt Book Fair, as specified in the Grant Agreement. The necessary space for the Mobile Immersive Book Box (MIBB) and a booth were booked within the ARTS+ Area, so Möbius could be presented together with other cross-media projects that involved technology, arts and literature, and whose stands were also of an interactive nature, in order to promote a curious and experimental mood among the visitors of Hall 4.0 that could facilitate their engagement in the piloting activities.

Outside of the MIBB, there was a small desk where the hostess/Möbius partners could interact with the participants. The Möbius booth had a corner assigned for the testing of the Virtual Reality Headsets, to avoid technical problems once the visitor was out of the bounded virtual space or even possible physical accidents with other visitors walking by. In addition to its organizational role in this event, the MVB staff was also actively involved in the piloting initiatives during the fair, inviting guests to test the Möbius Experiences.

MVB has also been actively disseminating in its own social media the different events and piloting activities organized by other consortium members to reach a bigger audience, as well as to target specialists to test the different outcomes of the project. Networking has been also a fundamental activity during this phase.

As the leader of the work package containing task 5.3, **Bookabook** assumed the responsibility of coordinating the work package from M18 onwards. In the tri-weekly meetings conducted between September 2022 and December 2023, Bookabook ensured the smooth and timely progress of task 5.3 development. Additionally, Bookabook participated in the Frankfurter Buchmesse, where piloting and testing activities occurred.

FMWC played an active role in Möbius' pilot activities within Task 5.3. As the coordinator of the WP on communication and dissemination (WP6), FMWC meticulously tailored communication campaigns for the participation of Möbius in each event, highlighting the specific pilot activities being showcased. These campaigns encompassed Twitter and LinkedIn copywriting, specifically designed email templates aimed at inviting potential visitors to various fairs, and eye-catching creativities for engaging social media posts. In addition, FMWC led the branding of each event.

FMWC's active presence extended to prominent industry events, including the London Book Fair, the Leipzig Book Fair, the Readmagine Madrid (2023), the international Broadcasting Convention in Amsterdam (2023), the Frankfurt Bookfair (2023), and the Mobile World Congress Barcelona (2024). Furthermore, FMWC, in collaboration with IMEC and DEN, organised two Möbius Book Creator Online Summer Workshops, fostering engagement and collaboration within our Möbius community.

FEP consistently supported Möbius' piloting activities, primarily focusing on the PIT due to its importance for publishers. FEP's efforts included networking, disseminating information about Möbius' outputs and pilots, actively participating in piloting events (such as Readmagine Madrid 2023), and presenting Möbius' tools during FEP's regular meetings to gather feedback, including a special demonstration in the meeting of November 2023.

KKW performed two events at its venue to show the finished immersive experiences both in the Möbius Immersive Book Box (MIBB) and in the Maschinenhalle: The Fantastic Adventure Night and the Bright Festival Connect. During the Bright Festival Connect the MIBB was presented and via survey feedback was collected from the visitors. Overall, the presentation of the MIBB and the VR-experience was prepared and installed by KKW at their venue.

KU LEUVEN actively participated in the piloting activities conducted in Leipzig, Germany, and maintained a constant line of communication with the piloting partners, namely IMEC, DEN, and ENOLL, as well as the technical partner IN2. This ongoing collaboration ensured that KU LEUVEN was able to provide valuable legal insights whenever needed, especially in relation to the outcomes of the piloting exercises.

IN2 played a crucial role in developing the Möbius Player, Creator, and the PIT for the piloting activities, maintaining continuous communication with the piloting partners. The iterative testing process necessitated constant updates from the partners to IN2 regarding the piloting procedure outcomes. **EUT**, overseeing all project activities, ensured seamless coordination among project partners.

1.2 Relation to Other activities

The Work Packages (WP) of the Möbius project are closely connected as the project follows an iterative development process. As seen in Figure 6, tasks in both WP2 and WP6 play a pivotal role across all activities. WP2 establishes foundations and baselines for piloting activities, while WP6 gathers progress and disseminates information, and fosters collaboration with relevant stakeholders.

Figure 6 Workflow of project tasks

This deliverable reports on the activities conducted within the task 5.3 *Open tests and evaluation* which tested and evaluated the Möbius Book Experiences generated in T5.1 *Möbius book productions* and T5.2 *Möbius experiences*. In addition, the applications tested were developed within WP3 *Prosumer intelligence and business models* and WP4 *Möbius Book*, and as such close collaboration with the technical partners was required. For this reason, regular meetings were organised by IMEC to review the user feedback and discuss the functionalities which were feasible to implement.

In addition, the activities reported in this deliverable are crucial for the completion of WP2 and the preparation of D2.4 *Möbius value proposition: an evaluation*, led by DEN. Specifically, it is during the piloting activities that are reported in D5.3 that data collection on the assessment of the Möbius products took place. The analysis of the data is part of WP2, while the resulting impact areas of the Möbius project and their significance are reported in D2.4 *Möbius value proposition: an evaluation*.

Any legal issues that arose during the piloting activities were carefully considered by KU LEUVEN in the development of both D3.3 *Interim Report on Prosumer Business Models and IP Framework*, and D3.5 *Final Report on Prosumer Business Models, Cross-sector Scalability, and IP Framework*. This comprehensive approach guaranteed that legal aspects were meticulously addressed throughout the project, significantly enhancing the overall quality and robustness of the reports.

Finally, WP6 *Maximizing Impact* has played a crucial role in advancing the Möbius Open Piloting initiative by establishing effective communication and dissemination channels. The FMWC team's efforts have primarily focused on event mapping and dissemination. FMWC initiated its contribution by meticulously mapping out a series of prominent events where the Möbius Book and Möbius Book Experiences could be featured and tested to gather valuable feedback. Notably, each event was accompanied by a dedicated blog post on the Möbius website, featuring images hosted on the project's Flickr account. Additionally, summary videos chronicling the journey at these events were produced. To ensure maximum reach and impact, FMWC prepared LinkedIn and event-specific communication messages, extending invitations to potential attendees and the Möbius target audience, encouraging them to explore our project and interact with our applications or provide valuable feedback on the Möbius Book Experiences. Möbius' branding was showcased at each event through the design and setup of exhibition booths. Informative flyers detailing the piloting activities procedure and comprehensive descriptions of the Möbius Book Experiences, based on the selected books "L'influenza del blu" by Giulio Ravizza and "Fantasy into Möbius" by Filippo Rubulotta, the Möbius Open Call winner, were thoughtfully prepared.

To raise awareness and engagement, a social media strategy was developed within WP6. This strategy was designed to promote all Möbius-related activities across various platforms, ensuring that the audience remained well-informed about Möbius participation in events, as well as in the organization of these events. FMWC has been proactively reaching out to subscribers of the Möbius newsletter, ensuring they were kept informed about Möbius ongoing participation in events and event planning. To facilitate effective communication, FMWC has designed and produced marketing materials tailored to the specific needs of Möbius project

partners. These materials served as valuable resources, providing detailed information about the different Möbius products, enabling Möbius partners to effectively communicate to their target audience. Moreover, all the Möbius stands at the attended events have been branded as per T6.1 *Dissemination and Communication*.

Overall, WP6 created a dynamic and effective communication strategy for the Möbius Open Piloting initiative, ensuring that all Möbius products and experiences reached the widest possible audience and received valuable feedback for further improvement.

For further information about the tools and channels used to attract the targeted audience, the blogposts on the Möbius website, newsletters issued, marketing materials, events, and the metrics used to evaluate, consult D6.4. *Maximising Impact Report*.

1.3 Methodology and approach

As outlined in the Grant Agreement, the events during Pilot Phase 3 were hosted in diverse settings, including public events such as fairs, and art exhibitions. These events also took place in local Living Labs, and at international events to ensure widespread user participation. Drawing from our experience during Pilot Phase 2, the piloting partners found that reaching participants was most effective through events or scheduled meetings where they could engage with testers. Hence, we strategically targeted various European book fairs and international events, aligning with Möbius' thematic focus on books.

In the context of Pilot Phase 3b, which included demonstration events, Möbius Book's fixed installation, facilitating collective immersive book experiences, was integrated into the program of KKW for one year. This installation proved to be the primary contributor to the target participant numbers. It was acknowledged already in the Grant Agreement that the majority of visitors in this case were locals from Leipzig.

The table below outlines the anticipated Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for Pilot Phase 3a, detailing the number of participants engaged and the specific Möbius outputs tested in six different geographical areas. These KPIs were first defined in the Grant Agreement, where it was established that the total goal for Pilot Phase 3 are 600 testers, with at least 100 testers per country. This goal was afterwards adapted through bilateral meetings with the partners, resulting in the target numbers presented in Figure 4. The target numbers were higher than the initial numbers set in the Grant Agreement. The table also demonstrates which output was tested at specific geographic areas. With regards to the Möbius Book, it

	Spain	Italy	Germany	Belgium	Finland	Poland
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Target number of participants (Pilot Phase 3a)	100	100	100	170	100	100
Output tested	Möbius Book and VR headsets	Möbius Book	Möbius Book and Immersive experiences	Möbius Book & Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit and VR headsets	Möbius Book	Möbius Book

Table 2. KPIs of Pilot Phase 3 per country

1.1.1 Target groups

The nature of the targeted groups involved in Pilot Phase 3 was diverse and varied according to the output tested. These ranged from professionals working in the book publishing industry, especially publishers and publishing houses representatives, booksellers, writers, illustrators, readers, and students attended the book fairs. Table 3 shows which end-users were targeted per product:

Möbius output	Target group
Möbius Player	Readers or people interested in the consumption of books. This also included professional users.
Möbius Creator	Writers, amateur or aspiring writers.
PIT	Publishers and stakeholders working in the publishing sector.
MIBB or Mobile Immersive Book Box	Visitors of the Frankfurt Book Fair, visitors of the KKW venue who are Leipzig locals.
Immersive experience	General public - Leipzig locals.
VR headsets	Leipzig locals, visitors of the Book Fairs and international events, readers, writers, tech enthusiasts.

Table 3. Möbius target groups

1.1.2 Evaluation Forms and questionnaires

Evaluating participants experience – User Requirement Survey

Regarding Pilot Phase 3a, running from M30 to M36, IMEC, in collaboration with DEN, prepared one questionnaire with open and general questions to evaluate the participants' experience with the Player, Creator, and PIT. The questionnaire contained, for all applications, 6 user evaluation questions and 4 questions collecting personal information of the respondent (age, gender, job, and email address). For the PIT, 3 additional questions were asked, mainly related to resources and business models. The more general questionnaire was formatted in a Google Form survey, so that it could be completed by participants during the events, such as book fairs. Although the original form was in English, partners were also given the opportunity to translate it into their native language if it was not convenient for them to do the survey in English at a particular event. Answers were automatically collected by IMEC via the English-language survey. If a partner had translated the survey into another language, they were asked to first translate the responses back into English and then, to forward them to IMEC. An informed consent to be filled during the events and after conducting the interview/survey, was also prepared. In this case, the purpose of the informed consent was to collect email addresses, to contact respondents with other project-related activities.

Impact assessment Survey

For the assessment of the Möbius Creator, Player and PIT, DEN developed questions which, in collaboration with IMEC, were incorporated together with the general assessment questions into Hotjar, to be filled during the testing of the Möbius products. The application did not work properly and, thus, DEN's approach to this was modified at the beginning of Pilot Phase 3a. In order to find the most efficient way for carrying out the impact assessment activities, DEN had discussions with interested partners (specifically, IMEC and ENoLL, and then, later, Laurea and KPT). As a result, DEN and IMEC developed questionnaires in Google Forms in English, which could be filled in on the spot (at the fairs and other events) by participants using iPads or other devices brought by the partners. A questionnaire with 20 questions was developed for the Möbius Creator, and one with 13 questions was developed for the Möbius Player. DEN and IMEC held additional meetings with the partners to explain the methodology, the reasoning behind it and how forms should be used. The questionnaires needed about 5-8 minutes to be filled in; they did not collect email addresses or other personal information. Access to these questionnaires was given to all the partners who run impact assessment activities and general evaluation activities. DEN was responsible for making sure that the online forms worked properly. All responses (anonymous) were collected directly by DEN. DEN shared the number of responses with the interested partners. Links to the online surveys were also sent to people who participated in online workshops by the respective partners leading the workshops. The form for the impact assessment of the Möbius Player was also translated in Italian by ENoLL and it was used briefly in an Italian context. A similar questionnaire on Google Form (with 14 questions) was also developed by DEN to assess the impact of the PIT. As often stated, this impact assessment survey also contained questions relevant to the User Requirement Survey.

For the Möbius immersive experiences, we followed a different approach at the beginning: for the first demonstration of the immersive experience at Leipzig (Fantastic Adventure Night), in

April 2023, we prepared questions that were asked to the visitors. The response rate was not very high. For the assessment of the MIBB during the Bright Festival Connect in Leipzig in October 2023, KKW administered their own questionnaire. For the subsequent events, we followed a more systematic approach, and we developed an online questionnaire (17 questions) using Google Forms that could be used to collect impact assessment data for the MIBB and the VR headsets. Similarly to the other questionnaires, the form was shared with all the partners carrying out the piloting. The form did not collect any personal data, and DEN was responsible for sharing the final numbers with the other piloting partners.

We believe that, for the case of the Möbius Player, Möbius Creator, and the Möbius Experiences this methodology was successful as it allowed DEN to collect data fast and uniformly, in a way that these could be analysed in line with the proposed methodology. The issues we encountered regarding data collection for the PIT should be attributed to the product and to the potential of attracting the interest of publishers, and not to the impact assessment methodology.

1.1.3 Incentives for participation and dissemination

During the piloting activities across various locations, similar incentives were employed to attract and engage participants:

Tote Bags, Pins, Notebooks:

- OPENLIVINGLAB DAYS 2023: Tote bags, pins, and notebooks were provided as incentives for participation and dissemination of the project.
- LIBER MADRID 2023: Participants received pins, tote bags, or notebooks as incentives.
- SALONE DEL LIBRO DI TORINO 2023: Möbius-branded tote bags, notebooks, stickers, earphones, and informative flyers were distributed to encourage survey completion and app testing.
- LEIPZIG BOOK FAIR 2023: Incentives included tote bags, notebooks, stickers, and informational flyers.
- INTERNATIONAL BROADCASTING CONVENTION AMSTERDAM 2023: Tote bags and notebooks featuring the Möbius logo, along with stickers and flyers, were distributed to encourage survey participation and Player testing.
- LONDON BOOK FAIR 2023: Möbius-branded tote bags and notebooks, along with stickers and flyers, were handed out to attract participants and encourage survey completion and app testing.
- VIENNA BOOK FAIR 2023: Incentives included Möbius-branded tote bags, pens, brooches, and flyers to encourage participation in surveys and app/VR experience testing.
- LJUBLJANA BOOK FAIR 2023: Showcased 100 Möbius-branded tote bags on booth shelves, along with flyers and QR codes for accessing applications. Candies and chocolate were also given, particularly to schoolchildren at the book fair.
- FRANKFURT BOOK FAIR 2023: Promotional materials and flyers.

Movie Tickets:

- FINLAND: Testers were rewarded with movie tickets for their time spent testing the apps.

Special Voucher and Promotional Pack:

POLAND: A "Thank You pack" was prepared, consisting of a special voucher for the Empik Go platform and a promotional pack. This incentive was given only to testers who confirmed survey completion. Empik Go is a platform which is addressed to readers, the platform with over 50,000 e-books, audiobooks, podcasts, and audio series. These varied strategies aimed to not only increase participant numbers but also to foster engagement and interaction with the Möbius project, contributing to the success of the piloting activities.

2. Möbius Pilot Phase 3

In this chapter reports from piloting activities held in different countries are presented. Each report includes the event name, place, country, date, piloting partners involved, the Pilot Phase in which the piloting activity belongs, results from the Pilot Phase, event description and piloting objectives, equipment and incentives for participation, audience and challenges and lessons learned.

2.1 Belgium

2.1.1 1-on-1 in-depth interviews

Location: Online - Microsoft Teams

Date: December 2023

Piloting partner: IMEC

Pilot Phase: 3a

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested			X		
Type of survey			User Requirement Survey was turned into an interactive interview format		
Number of testers reached			6		

Table 4. Online piloting session with 1-on-1 in-depth interviews

Event description and piloting objectives

The 1-on-1 in-depth interviews were conducted online via the Microsoft Teams platform to gather feedback and opinions from publishers on the Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit (PIT). To enhance the flow of the testing conducted with PIT, IMEC sought insights from European publishers regarding their perceptions and experiences with the tool. The primary objective was to understand how the PIT could be advantageous for both individuals and their organizations. To initiate the interviews, respondents were introduced to the PIT, allowing them to visually and experientially engage with the tool. This initial exposure aimed to provide participants with a tangible understanding of the capabilities of PIT and its potential impact on their work.

Equipment and incentives for participation

The interviews were conducted using Microsoft Teams to ensure the inclusion of publishers from various European locations. This platform was chosen not only to facilitate broad participation but also to enable IMEC to seamlessly record and transcribe the interviews through the software.

Audience

While the invited audience encompassed publishers from all over Europe, it is noteworthy that the initial three interviews exclusively featured participants from eastern and northern Europe.

Challenges and lessons learned

One of the main challenges has been engaging participants, especially because they were requested to indicate their availability before the Christmas holidays, which usually is a busy period. In total, IMEC wanted to carry out interviews with 70 publishers, but only six publishers accepted the invitation for an interview. Although IMEC received six positive responses, there were several publishers that declined participation for different reasons; among them, the main reasons were availability and lack of interest. Even after having sent reminders to respondents, the great majority of publishers contacted (130/140 publishers) did not respond to the invitation for an interview.

The interviews presented a challenge wherein the respondents struggled to grasp the origin and accessibility of the data in the PIT. Some misconceptions appeared: some participants believed the data would have been readily available through the PIT or that there would have been an existing data pool for insights into diverse markets. Others assumed it would have been difficult to access or collect data due to the perceived small size of their markets or communities; consequently, several interviews revolved around these notions. The level of interest varied among the respondents. Some of them expressed heightened interest in exploring the PIT's potential benefits, while others lacked enthusiasm, deeming the data insufficiently useful for their small market in the publishing sector. Their scepticism underscored the need for more useful data to make the tool more relevant and beneficial for their organization. A key takeaway is that the data presented did not sufficiently illustrate how the PIT could aid the publishers' organizations, especially for those uninterested in fandom communities. To address this challenge in the future, a clearer explanation of how publishers can integrate their data into the PIT may be necessary. Additionally, showcasing another integrated dataset could demonstrate the varied outputs and purposes based on different types of data, aiding in illustrating the tool's adaptability.

2.2.2 Brussels piloting event with targeted stakeholders

Location: Brussels, Belgium

Date: 18 December 2023

Piloting partner: ENoLL

Pilot Phase: 3b

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested				x	
Type of survey				Impact Assessment Survey	
Number of testers reached				12	

Table 5. Brussels piloting event with targeted stakeholders

Event description and piloting objectives

The Brussels piloting served both as a demonstration and a piloting opportunity. Positioned in close proximity to the European institutions and international organizations, this event strategically engaged a targeted audience from the public sector. Its primary goal was to showcase Möbius' innovative outputs, spark interest, and initiate discussions within the public sector representatives.

Equipment and incentives for participation

At the heart of the event were the VR headsets, capturing the spotlight and generating significant interest among participants. To express gratitude for their involvement, Möbius distributed branded tote bags to testers, creating a tangible connection between participants and the project. QR codes were provided for an impact assessment survey, enhancing the post-event evaluation process. Additionally, the event served as a platform for disseminating information about the Möbius project.

Audience

The audience comprised Brussels-based stakeholders, including representatives from European networks and the European Commission. Notably, key Living Lab representatives from various European countries attended the event. As Living Labs follow the iterative testing process and ensure the engagement of the quadruple helix, the event fostered lively discussions on the development of Möbius applications.

Challenges and lessons learned

The VR headsets garnered widespread enthusiasm, with participants expressing particular interest in the depiction of the book, notably the favoured "Influence of Blue." This positive reception sparked curiosity about the potential for developing more books using this immersive approach. Numerous inquiries were received about the Möbius applications, especially regarding overall connectivity and interoperability.

2.2 Spain

2.2.1 Readmagine Madrid

Location: Madrid, Spain

Date: 7 June 2023

Piloting partners: IMEC, FEP, FWMC

Pilot Phase: 3a

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested			x		
Type of survey			IMEC's User Requirement Survey was turned into an interactive workshop (using posters + post-its)		
Number of testers reached			18		

Table 6. Piloting event at Readmagine Madrid 2023

Event description and piloting objectives

ReadMagine is an annual event hosted in the Spanish capital, dedicated to conversations, workshops, conferences, meetings, and exchange of ideas around the process of transformation, reading and books. The piloting workshop was organised within the event programme. Given that publishers were the primary target for the PIT, conducting the workshop at this event, which saw a substantial presence of publishers, appeared to be a strategically sound decision. The overarching objective for the participating partners, including IMEC, FMWC, and FEP, was to acquaint workshop participants with the PIT and discern the specific data they envisioned incorporating into this tool.

IMEC, FMWC, and FEP were also looking for a publisher to share his/her data with them in the future, so that they could tailor the data in the PIT dashboard towards something more interesting to publishers.

Equipment and incentives for participation

For this online workshop, 1 personal computer and 2 smartphones to record answers were needed, as well as multiple posters with post-its.

Audience

The workshop was attended by 18 participants, that were divided between publishers and writers.

Challenges and lessons learned

The partners had only 45 minutes for the workshop, and this was too short to ask all planned questions and to have in-depth discussions. To address this issue, the workshop should be longer, at least one hour.

Figure 7. Piloting partners at Readmagine Madrid 2023

2.2.2 OpenLivingLab Days 2023

Location: Barcelona, Spain
Date: 21-23 September 2023
Piloting partner: ENOLL
Pilot Phase: 3a

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested	x	x		x	
Type of survey	User Requirement Survey	Impact Assessment Survey			
Number of testers reached	4	1		(no responses collected on the VR)	

Table 7. Piloting event at OpenLivingLab Days 2023

Event description and piloting objectives

OpenLivingLab Days is the flagship annual event organized by ENoLL. It is a highly anticipated gathering that brings together living labbers, public officials, corporate leaders, entrepreneurs, academics, and innovators from around the world. The event offers a unique platform for networking, exchanging best practices, and collaborating on cutting-edge projects and for reflecting on the latest trends and how to shape the future.

The 2023 edition of the OpenLivingLab Days was held in the city of Barcelona, Spain, from 21-23 September 2023. Piloting was done at the Möbius booth located at the Port Vell building of the World Trade Center, Barcelona, and by approaching the participants of the event.

Equipment and incentives for participation

The equipment used were two iPads rented by ENoLL and VR headsets provided by KKW, which are seen in Figure 8. To attract more participants to piloting activities, tote bags, pins and notebooks were provided. Each person who participated in the piloting received a tote bag or a notebook and a pin.

Audience

The attendees of the event were international expert innovators from different sectors. The conference saw global representation and professionals from all over Europe and the world. Many people interacted with the project representatives, but few of them showed interest in participating at the piloting.

Challenges and lessons learned

At the time of the testing, the Möbius player, the Möbius creator, and the PIT front-end were still in the same format as they were during the Pilot Phase 2. Therefore, ENoLL received many similar comments as during the previous Pilot Phase. Some testers questioned the sustainability of the apps and wondered how they were different from the existing ones – such as Apple books or Amazon. In addition, the team at the event struggled to set-up the VR Headsets since the instructions were not developed at that moment and therefore the survey was not conducted as the proper VR experience could not be shared with the participants.

ENoLL also received questions on the business models of these apps, which were difficult to answer since, at this stage, the project did not have a business plan in place.

Overall, ENoLL saw that the participants were very knowledgeable on the topic and had a lot of experience with similar book readers. They also provided useful insight into how these apps can be improved. Moreover, the participants questioned the link and narrative between the VR experience and the project and the web-app.

Figure 8. Piloting partners and participants in the OpenLivingLab Days 2023

2.2.3 LIBER - Madrid Book Fair

Location: Madrid, Spain.

Date: 3-6 October 2023

Piloting partner: ENoLL

Pilot Phase: 3a

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested	x	x		x	
Type of survey	User Requirement Survey; Impact Assessment Survey	User Requirement Survey		/	
Number of testers reached	61 User Requirement Survey; 8 Impact Assessment Survey	2		/	

Table 8. Piloting event at LIBER - Madrid Book Fair

Event description and piloting objectives

Madrid hosts the largest international meeting of the Spanish-language book industry with the celebration of LIBER, which throughout its 38 editions has established itself as the first exhibition dedicated to the Spanish-language book in Europe, and as the main centre for business and professional exchange. An event that offers the broadest overview of current publishing production with representation from all sectors of the book industry, and the participation of companies that offer services for the book industry, digital content, new publishers, self-publishing, and intellectual property.

The event, consolidated as the main business platform dedicated to Spanish-language publishing and one of the most important international meetings, is open to all book sectors, with a special focus on digital content, new publishers, self-publishing, and intellectual property.

For three intense days, LIBER brought together publishers, authors, literary agents, booksellers, distributors, and other agents in the sector in the same space, bringing together approximately 10,000 professionals. The meeting was complemented by a digital format that for 3 months allowed the promotion of commercial agreements and exchanges.

In addition to a space for commercial exchange, LIBER is also a meeting point for training, debate, and reflection through an extensive programme of professional and cultural activities that brings together personalities from the publishing sector and offers the opportunity to analyse the future of the book sector.

This piloting was done at the booth located on the main floor of the Madrid Book Fair, seen in Figure 9, and by approaching fair participants.

Equipment and incentives for participation

The equipment used were two iPads rented by ENOLL, two roll ups borrowed from FMWC and VR headsets provided by KKW. To attract more participants to piloting activities, pins, tote bags and notebooks were provided. Each person who participated in piloting received a pin, tote bag or a notebook.

Audience

Attendees of the event included publishers, authors, literary agents, booksellers, editors, translators, and other professionals from the publishing industry from different countries. The fair saw global representation and professionals from all over Europe and the world, with a huge bias towards the Spanish industry.

During the first two days, there was a huge influx of people; however, on the last day (Friday) the fair was quite empty. By that time, ENOLL staff at the booth already interacted with different people, including those at other booths.

Challenges and lessons learned

The concerns raised at the London Book Fair (Chapter 2.7.2) were echoed also in Madrid. In fact, the early development stage of the Player, the Creator received similar comments as during the previous Pilot Phase and brought a general feeling of disappointment. Some testers questioned the sustainability of the apps and its business model, suggesting different types of subscription, pay per use, or renting at local level in local libraries, but including the private sector. The questions related to the business model were difficult to answer since at this stage the project did not have a business plan in place. Therefore, the comments were collected but no answer was given.

Recommendation for further piloting activities is to target book fairs and other industry events where people are interested in the project, and to bring goodie bags to attract people to the booth and encourage them by providing incentives to do the testing.

The participants also provided useful insights into how these apps could be improved. Overall, we saw that the participants were very knowledgeable on the topic and had a lot of experience, with similar book readers. In general, two types of answers could be perceived: fond of the idea or completely disagree with it. Some of the participants considered that the questions were too time consuming and were not willing to answer the Impact Assessment Survey. However, all agreed on the potential of the project.

Figure 9. Views from LIBER - Madrid Book Fair 2023

2.2.4 Mataró Libraries

Location: Mataró, Spain
Date: 5 December 2023
Piloting partner: ENOLL
Pilot Phase: 3a

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested	x				
Type of survey	Impact Assessment Survey				
Number of testers reached	8				

Table 9. Piloting event at Mataró Libraries

Event description and piloting objectives

The Popular Library, in the city centre of Mataró, Spain, is located in the basement of the Iluro Foundation building where the Popular Library of the Foundation used to be. The spaces have been renovated to accommodate this new Mataró neighbourhood approach library. The library specialized in co-operatives has interest centres for language learning, popular culture, personal development, youth space, families, the world of work and travel and active tourism. There are numerous services for its users and a wide program of activities in the field of promoting reading for all audiences. The area for the piloting activity is seen in Figure 10

Equipment and incentives for participation

The equipment used was one iPhone 13 provided by ENOLL, two roll ups borrowed from FMWC, and furniture borrowed from the library.

Audience

People visiting the library did not show any interest towards Möbius; fair attendees proved to be much more curious. The majority of the library's daily users identified were high school students, university students, teachers, and older people.

Challenges and lessons learned

The concerns raised during the piloting at the library were surprisingly aligned with previous phases, but the general feeling was hopeful. Some testers questioned the sustainability of the apps and its business model, suggesting different types of subscription or pay per use, but always questioning why they should use the platform when they had the library, putting emphasis on the nature of the added value of the platform. The participants also provided useful insights into how these apps can be improved; for instance, the addition of a real time encyclopaedia that the user can use when he/she desires.

Figure 10. Views from Mataró Libraries

2.3 Italy

2.3.1 Salone Internazionale del Libro di Torino

Location: Turin, Italy

Date: 18-22 May 2023

Piloting partner: ENoLL

Pilot Phase: 3a

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested	x	x	x		

Type of survey	User Requirement Survey; Impact Assessment Survey (via email at a later stage)	User Requirement Survey	User Requirement Survey		
Number of testers reached	55 User Requirement Survey; 3 Impact Assessment Surveys	7	9		

Table 10. Piloting event at Salone del Libro di Torino

Event description and piloting objectives

The “Salone Internazionale del Libro di Torino” (<https://www.salonelibro.it/>) is the most important Italian publishing event, and one of the largest in Europe, where every year, in Turin, the whole book chain meets: publishing houses, writers, booksellers, librarians, agents, illustrators, translators and many readers. For publishers, the Salone is the key occasion for the sale and presentation of publishing news. For all readers, the Salone is a great international festival of culture: 2,000 guests from all over the world for a total of 1,200 events. Every year, the authors who have shaped the history of twentieth century and modern-day literature arrive at the Salone.

The Turin Book Fair hosts over a thousand publishers every year, from large groups to independents, in an exhibition itinerary along four pavilions. Publishing houses can participate with different types of stands, personalizing their presence at the fair with an ad hoc project. In 2023 the Salone hosted 215,000 visitors, 573 stands, 28,878 students and 2,000 accredited professionals.

ENoLL chose to pilot the Möbius applications at the Salone Internazionale del Libro di Torino because it is a prominent international book fair that draws diverse and numerous crowds of publishers, authors, and other book industry professionals from Italy and around the globe. This decision stems from the fair's extensive reach and ability to connect ENoLL with a wide range of stakeholders in the publishing world. Views from the piloting event are shown in Figure 11.

Equipment and incentives for participation

To demonstrate the Möbius applications, two iPads were rented specifically for the pilot testing sessions. Given that the initial survey forms were in English, ENoLL opted to translate them into Italian to facilitate the testing process. The primary testing location was the Möbius booth, situated within the Professional Area of the book fair. To attract more participants and encourage them to test the apps and fill in the surveys, ENoLL distributed Möbius-branded tote bags, notebooks, stickers, earphones (used during the testing activities and then gifted to the participants), and flyers providing comprehensive project information.

Audience

The event was attended by publishing houses, writers, booksellers, librarians, agents, illustrators, translators, readers, students, etc.

As presented in Table 10, 71 people tested the application (58 the Möbius Player, 7 the Möbius Creator, 9 the PIT), and at least 100 people approached the stand. The 9 PIT responses received were incomplete. This is likely due to the lack of in-depth application knowledge from the on-site partner, and the large number of questions in the PIT feedback form.

The impact assessment survey for the Möbius Player (only the participants of the Möbius Player piloting activities provided ENoLL staff their email addresses for future follow-up activities and feedback), translated in Italian, was sent in October 2023 to about 25 email address collected during the event; after this, DEN received feedback from only 3 users.

Challenges and lessons learned

In general, testers were pleasantly surprised; the parts that they enjoyed the most were the ambient audio and the images/videos linked to the text. Almost everyone agreed that the application was interesting and that it could be very useful both for bringing children closer to reading, and for people with learning disabilities.

Since testers could give their feedback in their native language, this likely contributed to them feeling more comfortable in expressing their honest opinions and giving feedback about the applications. On the other hand, the fact that the apps were all in English was not positively welcomed by many other testers.

Finally, testers also shared valuable insights on how to improve the Möbius applications.

Figure 11. Views from Salone Internazionale del Libro di Torino 2023

2.3.2 Italy Piloting Activity with Targeted Stakeholders

Location: Online

Date: 7-17 December 2023

Piloting partner: ENoLL

Pilot Phase: 3b

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested	x				
Type of survey	User Requirement Survey; Impact Assessment Survey				

Number of testers reached	20 User Requirement Surveys; 30 Impact Assessment Surveys				
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Table 11. Piloting activity in Italy with targeted stakeholders

Event description and piloting objectives

The Italy Piloting Activity with Targeted Stakeholders was an online initiative led by ENoLL to further enlarge the Italian component engaged in the piloting activities, besides the Salone Internazionale di Torino.

Italy is going through a wave of modernisation of the publishing sector, with always more initiatives focused on the importance of reading and how technology-oriented applications can empower the book industry, especially after years in which this industry was registering negative ratings. For this reason, through this initiative, ENoLL chose to focus more on the Italian public, to receive their inputs and feedback on Möbius applications.

Equipment and incentives for participation

The activity was not initially included in the event plan agreed with IMEC; for this reason, ENoLL decided to organize it as an online event where testers were involved in through an email.

To ensure a smooth experience for the different testers, and to guide them through the Möbius Player, ENoLL prepared a short video in Italian explaining how to surf through the application. In addition to this, ENoLL also provided the targeted stakeholders with detailed instructions on how to fill in the forms.

No incentives were included for the participation of testers.

Audience

The audience reached was very varied in terms of age, profession, and gender. The public was the targeted focus of the initiative; within them, students, writers, and readers were the main categories engaged. No publishers were engaged during this piloting.

During the 10-day initiative, both the User Requirement Survey and the Impact Assessment Survey were used and sent via email to the different stakeholders. A total of 50 responses were collected (20 for the User Requirement Survey; 30 for the Impact Assessment Survey). It is worth noticing that only the Möbius Player was tested.

Challenges and lessons learned

As the initiative was led online and mainly through emails, ENoLL did not have the chance to have a direct confrontation with all the people engaged. However, in some cases, the feedback was sent with comments about testers' experience, who underlined that the experience was

mainly positive, and who outlined a clear expression of interest about the next initiatives of Möbius and the future of its applications (especially, in this case, about the Möbius Player).

On the other hand, the discrepancy between the numbers reached by one form and the other may be caused by a language barrier. In fact, the targeted stakeholders filled in more DEN's Impact Assessment Surveys (10 more), with respect to the IMEC's User Requirement one, because the first one was probably faster and easier to fill. On the contrary, the IMEC form, containing more open questions, may have seemed difficult for some of the testers that were not so used to write (and explain themselves) in English.

2.4 Germany

2.4.1 Leipzig bookfair & Fantastic Adventure Night

Location: Leipzig

Date: 27 – 29 April 2023

Piloting partner: KKW, IMEC, FMWC, Bookabook, ENoLL

Pilot Phase: 3a & 3b

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Immersive experience	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested	x	x			x	x
Type of survey	User Requirement Survey	User Requirement Survey			Participatory observation	short interviews to 5 people, incorporating questions from the Impact Assessment Survey
Number of testers reached	29	6			150 visitors	70-80 visitors of the event

Table 12. Piloting event at the Leipzig bookfair & the Fantastic Adventure Night

Event description and piloting objectives

The first event took place between 27 – 29 April 2023, at the Leipzig Bookfair, for the book and media industry, connecting readers with authors, publishers, and media companies. Here, the different partners involved (KKW, IMEC, FMWC, Bookabook, and ENoLL) had a booth where they gave information on the project to passers-by, trying to gather feedback on the Player and the Creator.

The second event was the Fantastic Adventure Night on 28 April 2023. During this event, an art installation, and the Mobile Immersive Book Box led by KKW were shown to the different attendees. Here, the book 'Influence of the Blue' was projected in these installations for the first time.

Equipment and incentives for participation

For this piloting event, 2 iPads and 2 headphones were the main equipment used. The partners at the fair handed out tote bags, notebooks, stickers, and flyers with more information about the project as incentives for participation.

Audience

Readers, authors, publishers.

Challenges and lessons learned

A protocol was structured and shared with the partners prior to the event in order to streamline the process of data collection at Leipzig. The aim was to collect data for the two outputs adopting two different approaches, on the basis of the two different settings of the experiences. For this reason and due to the more static nature of the immersive experience, we decided that it was more appropriate to investigate it through participatory observation, unlike the MIBB, which we investigated through individual interviews to the participants, as people were free to enter and leave the box at their convenience. Accordingly, a protocol was structured for the observation of the immersive experience and a list of questions for interviewing the visitors to the Möbius box. In order to be ethically compliant with D1.3 *Ethical Requirements for Human Participation in Research*, the following additional material was prepared: i) informed consents to be signed by the people voluntarily participating in the interviews and ii) a disclaimer to be visible in the venue in order to alert people about the presence of researchers carrying out participatory observation.

The Möbius project was introduced to PAN e.V. (Phantastik-Autoren-Netzwerk (PAN) e.V.) – Network for authors of fantastic stories by representatives from KKW and VUB. They expressed keen interest in the process of transforming books into immersive experiences and proposed convening another meeting, potentially involving their management, in a virtual setting. A network meeting was held with PAN on 8 June 2023, during which it was revealed that the authors affiliated with PAN rely on publishers for adapting their books into other media.

Figure 12. Views from the Leipzig bookfair & the Fantastic Adventure Night

2.4.2 Frankfurt Book Fair

Location: Frankfurt, Germany

Date: 18-22 October 2023

Piloting partner: MVB, FMWC, DEN, IMEC, KKW, EUT, IN2

Pilot Phase: 3a & 3b

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested	x	x	x	x	x

Type of survey	User Requirement Survey	User Requirement Survey	User Requirement Survey	Impact Assessment Survey	Impact Assessment Survey
Number of testers reached	2	2	3	38	56

Table 13. Piloting at Frankfurt Book Fair

Event description and piloting objectives

The Frankfurt Book Fair is the world's largest trade fair in the publishing sector, and therefore an opportunity to access a wide range of public, from a younger non-professional audience to important stakeholders in the publishing sector. Because of this, the fair was defined in the Grant Agreement as the Möbius Final Event.

However, as the project was still in development at the time of the fair, the consortium adjusted its objectives. Instead of presenting finalized results, the focus shifted to unveiling pre-results to the project's target audience of professionals and prosumers, while also conducting piloting activities. The event provided an invaluable opportunity to showcase all products simultaneously, as seen in Figure 13.

The event offered the privilege of showcasing all products at once and the location of the Möbius booth in the ARTS+ area was excellent, next to a well visited TikTok Stand, the "Meet the Author" area and the Aldus Up stage with an active program on different topics including AI on the first day of the fair, where Möbius also had the chance to do a small presentation.

Equipment and incentives for participation

The following products and equipment were used:

- Mobile Immersive Book Box.
- 2 iPads to show the Player, Creator and PIT to the visitors.
- 4 VR headsets for the immersive experiences.

Audience

The audience was composed by an ample spectrum of visitors: from professionals of the book sector to literature enthusiasts. This variety is because the fair is opened for specialists and professionals during the week but for the public in the weekend.

It is very difficult to estimate the number of participants who interacted with Möbius productions, since there were hundreds of people passing by, coming in and coming out of the box and the personnel involved did not count them in a methodical way.

Many more attendees than those who filled out the surveys approached the Möbius booth and showed an interest in the project. We noticed many people who watched briefly the show in the MIBB and did not participate in the survey (either they spent too little time, or they did not want to take the survey, or left from the second exit and we were not able to talk to them)

Challenges and lessons learned

The challenges and lessons learned from the Frankfurt Book Fair, can be grouped according to the outputs tested:

- **Mobile Immersive Book Box:** A very short summary of *The Influence of Blue* was posted outside of the MIBB. People were able to move freely in and out of the MBB. Some seating was provided inside the box. Images were projected on 2 walls. There were some technical difficulties during the first day with the immersive experiences: the MIBB needed to be adapted to the conditions of the Frankfurt Book Fair (more light and noise, different environment from the KKW venue, where the box is normally located). KKW was able to solve the problem on the second day. It is imperative that an on-site technician is present at the events to avoid possible problems. Due to these issues the experience could be assessed from 20 October 2023, onward, which is also when the fair opened to the public.
- **VR headsets:** The VR headsets were set up for every viewing according to the instructions provided by KKW, and they were subsequently given to the interested audience members for viewing the show. The hand controllers did not need to be used by the audience.
- **Player & Creator:** During the weekend, on certain occasions, translations of the survey were required for visitors who only spoke German, which not only rendered the process tedious but also compromised its anonymity.
- **PIT:** A workshop was planned on Friday 20 October 2023. Unfortunately, only one participant took part in it and his background did not make him eligible for the assessment test. In light of the low attendance at the PIT workshop, it is imperative to recognize that many participating publishers at the Book Fair have busy schedules. While the Book Fair may have initially appeared to offer an ideal setting for such an endeavour, the practicality of engaging specialists during this event was limited.

Figure 13. Views from Frankfurt Book Fair

2.4.3 Bright Festival Connect

Location: Leipzig, Germany

Date: 12-15 October 2023

Piloting partner: KKW

Pilot Phase: 3b

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested					x

Type of survey					Survey in German by KKW
Number of testers reached					600-800 visitors (49 filled in the survey)

Table 14. Piloting at Bright Festival Connect

Event description and piloting objectives

During the Bright Festival Connect, the immersion experience entitled "The Influence of Blue" was showcased within the Möbius Immersive Book Box, housed within a large tent, operating from 11am to 7pm daily. The festival drew in a total of 2655 attendees, with an average of 600 to 800 visitors exploring the box. The exterior of it featured branding related to the Möbius project, and an iPad was stationed at the exit for survey completion.

Observations made by project representatives indicated that guests' visits to the MIBB were often brief, potentially due to prior exposure to similar immersions in the Maschinenhalle. This familiarity may have diminished the impact of the MIBB experience. A total of 49 survey responses were collected. In summary, while guests expressed high interest in the experience, there was a reluctance among many to complete the survey upon completing the visit.

Equipment and incentives for participation

Mobile Immersive Book Box and an iPad.

Audience

Locals from Leipzig, Germany.

Challenges and lessons learned

The audience response to the presentation of immersive shows varies significantly depending on the setting. When the show is presented in large halls with a notable introduction, the content tends to captivate the audience, eliciting a highly enthusiastic response. However, when the shows are presented within a walk-through box, such as the MIBB, people are less inclined to remain for the duration of the show. This observation led to the understanding that the MIBB presentation format is suitable for very short stories. Subsequently, requests were received regarding the potential use of the MIBB as a technical device for other content, targeting specific audiences.

Since KKW did not use the Impact Assessment Survey but incorporated some of the questions in their own survey, the answers will not be included in the total number of participants reached for the impact assessment.

2.5 Finland

Nine (9) workshops at Laurea University of Applied Sciences

Location: Finland (online and face-to-face)

Date: 20 September to 19 November 2023

Piloting partner: Laurea University of Applied Sciences

Pilot Phase: 3a

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested	X	X			
Type of survey	User Requirement Survey; Impact Assessment Survey	User Requirement Survey; Impact Assessment Survey			
Number of testers reached	24 User Requirement Surveys; 34 Impact Assessment Surveys	60 User Requirement Surveys; 90 Impact Assessment Surveys			

Table 15. Nine (9) workshops by Laurea University of Applied Sciences.

Event description and piloting objectives

Laurea University of Applied Sciences operates in Uusimaa region at six different campuses. There are about 9,900 students, 660 staff members and 34,700 alumni in the community. Fields of study in Laurea are Business Management, Social Services and Health Care and Hospitality Management. Laurea has 18 University degree programmes, six of which are taught in English.

As summarised in Table 16, 24 User Requirement Surveys were conducted for the Möbius Player and 60 for the Möbius Creator. Regarding the impact assessment survey, 34 responses were collected for the Player and 90 for the Creator in 6 online and 3 face-to-face workshops between 20 September and 19 November 2023. The testers were 25 to 50 –year old students or personnel from Laurea University of Applied Sciences. It is also imperative to note that the number of attendees to the workshops was higher than the number of responses submitted.

Piloting activity	Date	Player	Creator
Online workshop	20 September 2023		3 User Requirement Survey; 7 Impact Assessment survey
Online workshop	29 September 2023	5 User Requirement Survey; 5 Impact Assessment Survey	
Online workshop	2 October 2023		6 User Requirement Survey; 6 Impact Assessment Survey
Online workshop	6 October 2023		24 User Requirement Survey; 37 Impact Assessment Survey
Online workshop	9 October 2023		3 User Requirement Survey; 5 Impact Assessment Survey
Face to face workshop	16 October 2023	12 User Requirement Survey; 15 Impact Assessment Survey	6 User Requirement Survey; 12 Impact Assessment Survey
Face to face workshop	19 October 2023	5 User Requirement Survey; 5 Impact Assessment Survey	4 User Requirement Survey; 4 Impact Assessment Survey
Face to face workshop	9 November 2023		5 User Requirement Survey; 7 Impact Assessment Survey
Online workshop	17 November 2023	2 User Requirement Survey; 9 Impact Assessment Survey	9 User Requirement Survey; 12 Impact Assessment Survey
Total amount of tests		24 User Requirement Survey; 34 Impact Assessment Survey	60 User Requirement Survey; 90 Impact Assessment Survey

Table 16. Information about the 9 workshops led by Laurea University of Applied Science

Equipment and incentives for participation

The 6 online workshops were held via Microsoft Teams. The testers used their personal computers to test the apps and to answer the survey for the Impact Assessment and Open-ended questions (User Requirement Survey). The apps, the surveys, and the responses from the testers were all in English.

The workshops were held by two to three instructors. One of them gave instructions; the others observed the testing situation and helped the testers when needed (e.g., with technical questions).

The testing protocol was the same in both online and face to face workshops. The protocol was explained to the testers, and all of them were asked to sign the informed consent form using a digital google form. The Möbius book applications were introduced, and the testers were thereafter asked to try them themselves. The links to the applications were provided to the testers.

The time needed for testing the Möbius Player was 20 minutes, and for the Möbius Creator was about 45 minutes. After some time to explore the apps on their own, all testers answered the impact assessment and the open-ended questions surveys.

The testers were rewarded with movie tickets for their time used for testing the apps.

Audience

76% of the testers were students at Laurea University of Applied Sciences, and the remaining 24% were personnel from different campuses.

Challenges and lessons learned

The Möbius Creator required users to see a demo before they could use it. Some people expressed difficulties in understanding the logic of the app at first. However, at the end all testers managed to build a textbook with the app.

Using personal computers, different apps, and answering questionnaires is common for students and personnel in Laurea University of Applied Sciences. This made the testers excellent candidates for using apps like the Möbius Book. However, testers pointed out that step-by-step written instructions on how to use the Möbius Creator may be necessary in the future for most of the people.

The testers liked the apps, and it was a common comment that they started to visualize how they could use the apps in their life and work.

2.6 Poland

2.6.1 Infoshare Conference

Location: Gdańsk, Poland

Date: 24-25 May 2023

Piloting partner: KPT

Pilot Phase: 3a

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Book Box
Output tested	X				
Type of survey	User Requirement Survey translated in Polish				
Number of testers reached	2				

Table 17. Piloting at Infoshare Conference

Event description and piloting objectives

The Infoshare conference is a well-recognized event in Europe and worldwide, with a 16-year successful history behind. It has always been devoted to sharing practical knowledge among professionals, such as software developers, business leaders, start-up entrepreneurs, investors, marketing experts, and technology enthusiasts who come together to learn and be inspired by IT technologies. What started off as a modest event held at a university hall, has grown into a year-round celebration of technology.

The 2023 edition of the Infoshare conference (<https://infoshare.pl/conference/>) took place on 24-25 May 2023, in Gdańsk, Poland. It brought together thousands of individuals seeking a platform for networking and development, making Infoshare the largest technological and start-up event in Central and Eastern Europe. Over 6,000 people joined the conference for this 2-day event at the junction of business, technology, and marketing.

KPT chose this event because it attracts many attendees each year. KPT's goal was to conduct several initial tests on the Möbius Player during the conference and then, to collect feedback through surveys, which KPT translated into Polish.

Equipment and incentives for participation

The tests were conducted by 3 people involved in the project on behalf of KPT.

The staff at the conference used a laptop for navigating through the application, and a tablet for conducting and collecting survey responses.

Audience

The participants to the event were mainly participants to the conference and professional in the IT industry, specifically involved in new technologies and related fields.

KPT actively participated in the event, by interacting with event participants. The staff did not have a dedicated booth. As the staff at the conference received the surveys just before the event, they managed to test only 2 users (for the Möbius Player), while the Möbius Creator was not ready for testing.

Challenges and lessons learned

The testers mainly complained about the limited selection of reading materials. Additionally, they suggested that there were already many similar applications in the market, making it challenging to stand out, as they emphasized that currently available applications have a more intuitive interface.

Testers also highlighted that the application is not entirely modern in its design: using a browser is not currently popular, and each tester commented that they usually prefer to download ready-made applications from stores like Google Play or the App Store. The detailed report has been delivered to IMEC.

KPT did not encounter difficulties during the testing process. The application functioned correctly. However, KPT had to translate the survey into Polish to ensure that the questions were understandable to individuals with a limited knowledge of the English language. To have the testers giving responses in their native language contributed to their comfort in expressing all their thoughts and feedback about the application.

Figure 14. Views from the Infoshare Conference 2023

2.6.2 Piloting in the ecosystem of Krakow companies

Location: Krakow, Poland
Date: 3 June – 31 October 2023
Piloting partner: KPT
Pilot Phase: 3a

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested	X	X			
Type of survey	User Requirement Survey; Impact Assessment Survey, both translated in Polish	User Requirement Survey; Impact Assessment Survey, both translated in Polish			

Number of testers reached	119 User Requirement Survey; 53 Impact Assessment Surveys	4 User Requirement Survey; 6 Impact Assessment Surveys			
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Table 18. Piloting activities in the ecosystem of Krakow companies

Event description and piloting objectives

Since June 2023, representatives of the KPT team involved in the Möbius project, organised and conducted tests in various communities: at universities, job fairs for school graduates, during meetings at local activity centres, and, last but not least, during the International Book Fair in Kraków.

Based on the 4-person team involved in the project, KPT participated in numerous events, such as meetings at libraries, meetings during tech events organised by KPT, as well as at the partnering universities and other similar activities, all aimed at promoting the application as much as possible and identifying potential testers for the Möbius Player and Möbius Creator.

For the Möbius Creator, the tests were conducted by representatives of well-known publishing agencies. KPT also leveraged its contacts and relied on the KPT ecosystem and organized internal and external meetings with potential users. Listing only the most important ones, it's worth mentioning:

- Social Innovations Demo Days, #SDG48h Challenge – 16 June 2023.
- Summer Jam Event - July 4th, 2023.
- International Book Fair in Krakow – 26-29 October 2023.

The events were chosen precisely to bring and invite varied groups of stakeholders to the testing phase of the Möbius Player. The tests undertaken in June and July 2023 aimed to deliver fresh ideas about the optimal time and effective ways of conducting the surveys (e.g., place, time, targeted testers, their age, etc.). The intensive pilot testing began in June 2023 and lasted till the end of October 2023.

Moreover, to reach the targeted audience, KPT also initiated cooperation with a network of public libraries starting from Malopolska Regional (Provincial) Public Library in Krakow, City Public Library in Skawina, and Regional Public Libraries in Świętokrzyskie and Podkarpackie Voivodeships, to meet individual testers especially coming from smaller cities than Kraków.

KPT's goal was to conduct several initial tests of the Player and Creator application and then gather responses through surveys. All tests were conducted in Polish and the forms, also in Polish, were used to collect the feedback.

Equipment and incentives for participation

The staff at the piloting used a laptop for navigating through the application, and a tablet for conducting and collecting survey responses.

The staff did not have a dedicated booth, as the meetings were organized alongside the conferences (e.g., workshops, hackathons, etc).

To increase the number of potential testers, KPT prepared a special “Thank-you-pack” that included a special voucher for the Empik Go platform and a promotion pack. Empik Go is a platform with over 50,000 e-books, audiobooks, podcasts, and audio series. Access to the full library is possible thanks to a subscription that allows users to listen and play their favourite content via an application for phones and tablets. Only those testers who confirmed the completion of the survey were rewarded with the “Thank-you-pack” and voucher.

Figure 15 Promotion pack developed by KPT

Audience

The participants of the internal and external meetings, as well as of the organized events, represented varied groups of stakeholders, covering the quadruple helix: academia, business, administration, activists. The testers represented various sectors such as promotion & marketing, architecture, design, psychology, sales, IT sector, officials, landscape architecture, software, researchers, analysts, students, seniors (retired), and many others.

Challenges and lessons learned

KPT encountered no difficulties during the testing process. The applications functioned correctly.

However, KPT had to translate the survey into Polish, to ensure that the questions were understandable to individuals with a limited knowledge of the English language.

To have the testers giving responses in their native language contributed to their comfort in expressing all their thoughts and feedback about the application. Some more testers were interested in undertaking the survey and agreed to contact KPT to organize individual appointments with them, but this did not happen.

Figure 16 and 18. Views from piloting activities in the ecosystem of Krakow companies

2.7 Other countries

This sub-chapter will include reports on the piloting activities in the UK, the Netherlands, Austria and Slovenia; these countries were selected to enlarge the geographic outreach of the project and include more diverse stakeholders in the piloting activities.

2.7.1 International Broadcasting Convention

Location: Amsterdam, Netherlands

Date: 15-17 September 2023

Piloting partner: IMEC, FMWC, DEN

Pilot Phase: 3a

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested	x				
Type of survey	User Requirement Survey, Impact Assessment Survey				
Number of testers reached	8 User Requirement Survey, 14 Impact Assessment Surveys				

Table 19. Piloting at the International Broadcasting Convention 2023 in Amsterdam

Event description and piloting objectives

The International Broadcasting Convention (IBC) is an annual conference and exhibition for professionals involved in creating, managing, and delivering electronic media and entertainment. IMEC, FMWC, and DEN attended this event for dissemination purposes, as well as an opportunity to conduct some pilot activities.

The partners focused on the Möbius Player, since this application allows a general audience to be approached, as opposed to the Möbius Creator and the PIT.

Equipment and incentives for participation

For this piloting activity, IMEC, FMWC, and DEN used 2 iPads and 2 headphones. To encourage more people to participate in the survey and test the Möbius Player, IMEC, FMWC, and DEN handed out tote bags and notebooks with the Möbius logo. Stickers and flyers with more information about the project were also distributed.

Audience

People from the media, entertainment, and tech industries were present at the event. About 22 people tested the Möbius Player: 8 people filled in the open-ended questions (User Requirement Survey) and 14 people filled in the Impact Assessment Survey by DEN.

Challenges and lessons learned

Passers-by were interested in receiving information about the project, but often did not have the time to complete the survey or answer some questions. This could possibly be because the audience was very different from the target audience of the project. A possible solution to have more testers could be to leave the stand and interact with people at the event.

Figure 17. Views from International Broadcasting Convention

2.7.2 London Book Fair

Location: London, United Kingdom

Date: 18-20 April 2023

Piloting partners: ENOLL, FMWC

Pilot Phase: 3a

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested	x	x	x		
Type of survey	User Requirement Survey	User Requirement Survey	User Requirement Survey		
Number of testers reached	56	6	3		

Table 20. Piloting at the London Book Fair

Event description and piloting objectives

The London Book Fair (<https://www.londonbookfair.co.uk/>) is an annual book-publishing trade fair. It is a “global marketplace for rights negotiation and the sale and distribution of content across print, audio, TV, film and digital channels,” which is evident from the types of participants attending the fair. These were mainly professionals working in the book publishing industry, including authors, publishers, copyright professionals, commissioners, and the global licensors. The event gathers the global publishing community for three days. Since its launch in 1971, the fair has grown in size and importance, and it is considered as second in importance after the Frankfurt Book Fair. The 2023 edition was reportedly attended by more than 30,000 people.

We have chosen to pilot the Möbius applications at the London Book Fair because of its unique demographic of visitors, as it is an international fair that attracts publishers, authors and other professionals working in the book-publishing industry from all over the world. With that, ENoLL was able to increase the geographic outreach of the project and include more diverse stakeholders in the piloting activities. ENoLL’s aim was to pilot the apps with 60 users.

Equipment and incentives for participation

The applications were showcased on two iPads that were rented for the purposes of the piloting activities. As the applications and the survey form are dependent on an internet connection, ENoLL had to purchase an additional Wi-Fi connection for one of the iPads. Piloting primarily took place at the Möbius booth, but also by proactively approaching the participants of the fair and asking for their feedback. To attract more people and to encourage them to complete the survey and test the apps, Möbius branded tote bags and notebooks were handed out, in addition to stickers and flyers providing more information about the project.

Audience

Attendees of the event included publishers, authors, literary agents, booksellers, editors, translators, and other professionals from the publishing industry from different countries all over Europe and the world. Based on the tracker app provided to ENoLL with the Möbius booth, 77 people scanned the booth code; however, the number of people interacting with the partners at the booth was larger, as not everyone was interested in scanning the participant badge.

Challenges and lessons learned

In April 2023, when the Möbius Player, the Möbius Creator and the PIT were tested at the London Book Fair, the front-end features were still in the same format as they were during Pilot Phase 2. Therefore, ENoLL received many similar comments as during the previous Pilot Phase. Some testers questioned the sustainability of the apps, and wondered how they were different from the existing ones – such as Apple books or Amazon. ENoLL also received questions on the business models of these apps, which were difficult to answer since at this stage the project did not have a business plan in place. Overall, ENoLL saw that the participants were very knowledgeable on the topic and had a lot of experience with similar

book readers. They also provided useful insight into how these apps can be improved. All responses and tips received were recorded through the feedback form.

Figure 18. Booth at the London Book Fair

2.7.3 Buch Wien - Vienna Book Fair

Location: Vienna, Austria
Date: 8-12 November 2023
Piloting partner: ENoLL
Pilot Phase: 3b

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested	x	x		x	

Type of survey	User Requirement Survey, Impact Assessment Survey	User Requirement Survey, Impact Assessment Survey		Impact Assessment Survey	
Number of testers reached	2 User Requirement Survey; 18 Impact Assessment Survey	1 User Requirement Survey		6	

Table 21. Piloting at Buch Wien - Vienna Book Fair

Event description and piloting objectives

Buch Wien (<https://www.buchwien.at/>) is an annual international book fair held in November, doubling as a reading festival week that has become a staple of literary culture in the region and beyond since its inception in 2008. Organized by "Literature und Content Marketing GmbH," this event has established itself as one of the main events in Austria's literary calendar, serving as a platform for showcasing new releases of the autumn book season and as a forum for the exchange of ideas and opinions. The fair covers a wide range of topics, with both current societal and political discussions as well as literary trends and innovations taking center stage. The unique format of Buch Wien combines the traditional elements of a book fair with those of a reading festival week. Events are spread across the entire Vienna urban area, offering a mix of book presentations, readings, panel discussions, and lectures by both German-speaking and international authors. In this way, major contemporary issues are addressed and discussed. A highlight of Buch Wien is the awarding of the Austrian Book Prize, which honours outstanding literary achievements and awards authors in various categories. This honour attracts additional attention from media and literature enthusiasts and contributes to the significance of the event. The main events of the fair take place at Messe Wien, a modern exhibition venue that offers an inspiring atmosphere for exhibitors and visitors alike. With its far-reaching significance for the Austrian book industry, Buch Wien has established itself as a place of inspiration, exchange, and lively engagement with literature.

ENoLL chose the Buch Wien as a pilot site for the Möbius applications and VR experience because of its broad, diverse, and international audience. In fact, the fair attracts authors from around the world, providing an excellent opportunity to test the project's applications (with a focus on the Möbius Player) and the VR experience with a wide range of users.

Equipment and incentives for participation

To demonstrate the Möbius applications, two iPads were rented specifically for the pilot testing sessions. The survey forms used were the ones created by IMEC (User Requirement Survey) and DEN (Impact Assessment Survey). In addition to the surveys, two VR headsets, provided by KKW, were used to showcase the immersive experience at the booth.

To attract more participants and encourage them to both complete the survey and test the apps and the VR experience, ENoLL distributed Möbius-branded tote bags, pens, pins, and flyers providing comprehensive project information.

Audience

Attendees of the event included publishers, authors, literary agents, booksellers, editors, translators, other professionals from the publishing industry from different countries, mainly German speaking, and middle or high school students and teachers. The fair, aside from a huge presence of the German industry, also saw global representation and professionals from all over Europe and the world.

At least 150 people approached the stand.

Challenges and lessons learned

In general, testers were pleasantly surprised. Overall, the participants were knowledgeable on the topic and had a lot of experience with similar book platforms. Two types of answers could be perceived: fond of the idea or totally disagree with it; however, all agreed on the potential the project has. The participants provided additional useful insights into how the app could be improved (e.g., on how the user interacts with the platform, comment section, etc.), that were reported in the feedback forms. In addition, all participants who tried the VR experience were very impressed by it.

The language used for the tests was English, as the colleagues did not speak German, and ENoLL thought that this may have created a barrier between ENoLL staff at the fair and the audience, who perhaps was unable to convey all thoughts in another language, or simply did not want to speak another language other than the native one. Furthermore, the fair was visited by many young people in middle or high school; this meant that many people could not be interviewed.

Figure 19. Views from Buch Wien - Vienna Book Fair

2.7.4 Ljubljana knjižni sejem - Ljubljana Book Fair

Location: Ljubljana, Slovenia

Date: 21-24 November 2023

Piloting partner: ENOLL

Pilot Phase: 3b

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested	x	x		x	
Type of survey	Impact Assessment Survey	Impact Assessment Survey		Impact Assessment Survey	
Number of testers reached	3	3		56	

Table 22. Piloting at Ljubljana knjižni sejem – Ljubljana Book Fair

Event description and piloting objectives

The Slovenian Book Fair (SKS) (<https://knjizni-sejem.si/>) is one of the most important literary and cultural events in Slovenia, bringing together book lovers, authors, publishers, booksellers, and all those who appreciate the power of words and literature. The 2023 edition has been the 39th of this annual event, which offers a platform for research, promotion, and celebration of the Slovenian and foreign book culture. For the second year, the fair was held in the Ljubljana Economic Exhibition Centre, attracting thousands of visitors from all over Slovenia.

Some of the most important Slovenian publishing houses, as well as some foreign ones, presented themselves at the fair, exhibiting the most recent or most sold editions of books, from fiction to professional works. During the fair, visitors had both the chance to buy books and to follow the rich collateral program, taking part in many different events (i.e., presentations of books, authors, literary debates, workshops, and many others) that made the fair even more attractive.

Thanks to its utmost importance within countries of Central Europe, the Slovenian Book Fair was chosen to pilot the Möbius applications, to extend even more the European coverage of the project and to include more diverse stakeholders in the piloting activities. Furthermore, as data on the VR headsets were missing, ENoLL's aim at this event was to test them in this occasion, giving space to this tool, but still considering – and testing – the other applications (in particular, the Möbius Player and Möbius Creator).

Equipment and incentives for participation

The applications were showcased on two iPads that were rented for the purposes of the piloting activities. Both the applications, the survey form, and the impact assessments were dependent on the internet connection, but after asking the fair organizers for the password for the free Wi-Fi connection, ENoLL was able to use them without any further issues. In addition to the surveys, two VR headsets, provided by KKW, were showcased at the booth.

To attract more people and to encourage them to complete the survey and test the apps, 100 Möbius branded tote bags were showcased on the booth shelves, in addition to flyers providing more information about the project and the different QR codes to access the Möbius applications. Finally, as the book fair was largely attended by schools of all different levels and many children, ENoLL partners at the booth brought candies and chocolate to give to fair participants, however testing was not conducted with minors.

Audience

The nature of audience at the book fair was deeply diverse. Different professionals working in the book publishing industry, especially publishers and publishing houses representatives, booksellers, writers, illustrators, readers, and students attended the fair and reached ENoLL staff at the Möbius stand.

From 21 November to 24 November 2023, more than 150 visitors – among whom 120 students – tried the VR headsets; among them, a small percentage also tried the Möbius Creator. All those who tested the Möbius Creator, also went through the Möbius Player. Many other people interacted with the partners at the booth, asking for information about the project without testing the applications or the VR headsets; everyone was very interested in the project, in the technology used, and in the following commercialization phase.

A total of 62 responses were collected through the Impact Assessment survey; respectively, ENoLL staff gathered 56 responses for the VR headsets experience, 3 for the Möbius Player, and 3 for the Möbius Creator.

Challenges and lessons learned

During the Ljubljana Book Fair, significant interest was shown to the project, its applications, and future steps. Most testers enjoyed the immersive experience with the VR headsets. Many of them were also fascinated by the Möbius Creator and the 3D audio of the Möbius Player, professing their willingness to register to the application, create their own book, and enjoy the reading of the books already published there. Most visitors got additional flyers to bring to people at home or, as in the case of 2/3 of schoolteachers and several students, to their schools.

Within those who tested the applications and VRs headsets, most of them were relieved once informed that the forms did not require them to share sensitive data (i.e., name and surname, and email).

On the other hand, a high percentage of visitors and VR testers, mainly students, were disappointed by the fact that the VR experience “simply” reproduced a video instead of a more interactive experience (such as videogames). In addition, some of those who were interested questioned ENoLL staff about the home-replicability of VR headsets when reading, especially due to the high costs of the technology.

It is worth noting that, especially among younger generations, a quite important percentage of visitors were interested in the project but did not want to test the VR headsets. Moreover,

among those who tried them, some people got scared – or felt dizziness – after few seconds of testing.

Regarding older generations, many elderly people did not show interest in the project, especially once they understood that it implied the use of technology. However, even if they did not have a direct interest, some of them asked ENOLL staff to give them flyers for their grandchildren and other family members.

Overall, the pilot activity at the Slovenia Book Fair was very useful in terms of collecting data and feedback for the upcoming commercialization phase. It should be pointed out that the VR technology connected to books – and the reading process in general – was both positively welcomed by kids and users between 20- and 40-year-old, while negatively regarded by teenagers, and almost completely avoided by elder adults. For what concerns the applications, almost everyone, from the different categories and ages who agreed to be interviewed, valued positively the applications. Some snapshots from the book fair are seen in Figure 20.

Figure 20. Ljubljana knjižni sejem – Ljubljana Book Fair

2.8. Online Events

2.8.1. Workshop: Test with us the Möbius Creator I

Location: Online, Microsoft Teams

Date: 20 July 2023

Piloting partner: IMEC, DEN, FMWC

Pilot Phase: 3a

Participants: 15

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested		x			
Type of survey		IMEC's User Requirement Survey was turned into an interactive workshop with answers gathered via Miro Board; Impact Assessment Survey			
Number of testers reached		15 via Miro Board 9 User Requirement Survey, 6 Impact Assessment Surveys			

Table 23. Online Workshop: Test with the Möbius Creator I

Event description and piloting objectives

This event represented the first online workshop of summer 2023, dedicated to testing the Möbius Creator. The Möbius project decided to organise online workshops during the summer period in order to increase engagement in the piloting activities.

The Möbius Creator is an app that requires users to see a demo before they can use it. This is why it seemed a good idea to conduct a workshop on it. In this workshop, the plan was to provide participants with a general idea of what the Möbius Creator can do. This was done by first giving a tutorial on the Möbius Creator, then giving the participants time to explore the Creator on their own. Finally, IMEC, DEN, and FMWC tried to generate feedback from the participants.

Equipment and incentives for participation

For this online workshop, only a personal computer was used.

Audience

The workshop saw a participation of 15 valid participants.

Challenges and lessons learned

The first issue with this type of online workshops, is that despite the fact that a fair amount of people registered for the workshop, a much smaller amount of people ended up participating.

An additional difficulty was in receiving feedback (especially oral). To solve this, IMEC, DEN, and FMWC tried to collect feedback as much as possible through an online collaboration board called Miro.

Regarding the impact assessment, participants to the workshop signed a consent form and provided their email addresses so that they could be contacted with the impact assessment survey. Despite multiple reminders, only 6 out of the 15 participants filled in the form, highlighting the need for a revised strategy.

Figure 21. Workshop: Test with us the Möbius Creator I

2.8.2. Workshop: Test with us the Möbius Creator II

Location: Online, Microsoft Teams

Date: 07 August 2023

Piloting partner: IMEC, DEN, FMWC

Pilot Phase: 3a

Participants: 8

	Möbius Player	Möbius Creator	Prosumer Intelligence Toolkit	VR headsets	Mobile Immersive Book Box
Output tested		x			
Type of survey		IMEC's User requirement Survey was turned into an interactive workshop with answers gathered via Miro Board; Impact Assessment Survey			
Number of testers reached		8 via Miro Board; 5 Impact Assessment Surveys			

Table 24. Online Workshop: Test with us the Möbius Creator II

Event description and piloting objectives

IMEC, DEN, and FMWC conducted a second online workshop for Möbius Creator in August 2023. The workshop's main objective was to collect feedback on the current browser-based application. Participants actively engaged in an interactive exercise and completed a survey, providing valuable insights that will guide the project partners involved in improving the existing prototype. The input from workshop participants was instrumental in identifying strengths and areas for enhancement.

Equipment and incentives for participation

For this online workshop, only a personal computer was used.

Audience

The workshop saw a participation of 8 valid participants.

Challenges and lessons learned

The second online workshop presented similar challenges as the first one.

The difficulty with this type of online workshop was in receiving feedback (especially oral). Participants seemed mainly interested in testing the Möbius Creator, but not so much in giving feedback. For the participants, this could also be related with fear of public speaking. To mitigate this, IMEC, DEN, and FMWC tried to collect answers as much as possible through an online collaboration board called Miro.

Regarding the impact assessment survey, following the lessons learned from the previous workshop, we asked participants to fill in the impact assessment surveys at the end of the workshop, while they were still online. From the 8 participants, 5 filled in the survey, which is a higher percentage of participation than in the first workshop (62.5% vs 40%) indicating that the change of strategy was successful.

Figure 22. Workshop: Test with us the Möbius Creator II

Other online meetings

FEP has also used its regular meetings to host info sessions on the project and its events, including piloting opportunities. FEP meetings are regular gathering of FEP members (national publishers' associations) and other stakeholders, to cover both administrative and non-administrative tasks. During the FEP meeting of November 2023, FEP held a special demonstration session on the PIT, aimed at showcasing its latest iteration and to gather feedback on it. FEP created ad hoc materials that users could access before and after the event, to explore the PIT at their own time and provide feedback when appropriate. These included presentations and textual guides.

Throughout the project, FEP leveraged its network to connect the publishing sector with Möbius. FEP has regularly informed its contacts (from book fairs, other projects, and other sectors – such as academia) of opportunities regarding Möbius. FEP has also kept the Young Publishing Professionals alumni informed of the project, providing them materials to test the PIT independently. One publisher completed the User Requirement Survey.

Recommendations and lessons learned

The Recommendations and Lessons Learned chapter serves as a culmination of insights gleaned from navigating the complexities of piloting events and engaging with diverse stakeholders. Within this chapter, we distil the challenges encountered into actionable recommendations, offering a roadmap for future endeavours. From aligning with technical partners to navigating market dynamics, the lessons learned underscore the importance of adaptability, collaboration, and foresight in driving meaningful impact.

The User Requirement Survey was the most used at different events. That is because the survey was already created in April 2023 when the first piloting events were held. Conversely, the Impact Assessment Survey for the Player, Creator and the PIT was first launched online, but this has shown to be ineffective and the version which could be shown at piloting events was later developed in July 2023. The following responses were recorded for the User Requirement Survey (including workshops and interviews conducted by IMEC) for the different Möbius outputs:

- Möbius Player: 382
- Möbius Creator: 111
- PIT: 40

The highest number of answers was received for the Player since it entailed the easiest target group to reach and engage. On the other hand, PIT received the lowest number of responses, since it was difficult to engage the publishers in testing the tool, despite substantial efforts by the partners in reaching out to the publishers. The User Requirement Survey was not administered for the VR headsets, the Mobile Immersive Book Box, or the Immersive Experience.

Regarding the Impact Assessment Survey, the numbers of users reached at piloting events and meetings are lower, since the survey was deployed in the later stage of the Pilot Phase 3. The following numbers of survey respondents per output was reached:

- Möbius Player: 171
- Möbius Creator: 111
- PIT: 3
- VR headsets: 112
- Mobile Immersive Book Box: 56

Further discussion and assessment on the results from the User Requirement and Impact Assessment Surveys will be presented in Deliverable 2.4 *Möbius value proposition: an evaluation*.

The most common challenges encountered during the piloting events were:

- **Difficulty in reaching publishers, resulting in low response rates for feedback on the PIT:** It was shown challenging to attract publishers to test the PIT despite numerous efforts. During the Frankfurt Book Fair event for instance, efforts to schedule interviews

with 70 publishers resulted in only three acceptances. Despite reminders, most of the contacted publishers did not respond, highlighting challenges in securing responses from busy respondents.

- **Challenges in grasping PIT data accessibility:** Respondents struggled to understand the origin and accessibility of data in the PIT, leading to misconceptions about its usefulness. Clearer explanation and demonstration of PIT integration may be necessary to address these challenges.
- **Perceived lack of differentiation in apps:** During testing at various events, testers questioned the sustainability and differentiation of the project's apps compared to existing ones, already available on the market.
- **Lack of understanding of business models and usability of the applications:** At numerous piloting events, the participants posed questions about the fees associated with the Möbius applications, which were not addressed as the business model was developed at the end of the project. Further information can be found in D6.5 Möbius marketplace. It would have been more efficient to have finalised the business model at an earlier stage, in order to test its feasibility and adaptability by the end-users.
- **Technical challenges:** Technical difficulties during immersive experiences, encountered at events like the Frankfurt Book Fair or the OpenLivingLab Days, necessitated on-site technician support or better instructions shared with the on-site team.
- **Audience preferences and language barriers:** Concerns were raised about limited reading materials and language barriers in numerous countries, since the Player and the Creator are only available in English. Suggestions for improvements included enhancing language preferences and modernizing app design.
- **Interest and feedback collection challenges at digital workshops:** Challenges in collecting oral feedback were observed at online workshops. Adoption of online collaboration boards like Miro was attempted to address these challenges.
- **Varied reactions at different events:** Mixed reactions were observed at different events, with positive reception among certain age groups and scepticism from others. Feedback collection methods varied based on event type, with challenges in receiving oral feedback during online workshops.

Apart from the challenges identified from the end-users, the consortium encountered additional hurdles. Firstly, there was difficulty in synchronizing with the technical partners and the piloting events. This was because the piloting could only commence once the applications and immersive experiences were fully developed. However, there was limited flexibility regarding the timing of the events, as these took place during international fairs with fixed timelines. These events were particularly concentrated during the Spring and Fall periods, with fewer activities during the summer due to the holiday season. In turn, this also blurred the lines between the Pilot Phases 3a and 3b, as certain outputs, such as the VR headsets were only available for testing from September 2023 onwards and were tested at events scheduled from November 2023 until the end of the project.

Secondly, participants were often overwhelmed with the number of questions raised and therefore the testers had to focus either on the User Requirement Survey or the Impact Assessment Survey. Since the Impact Assessment form was developed in July 2023, during

the latter part of the piloting activities (in particular, during Pilot Phase 3b), we focused on using this form with participants.

During the pre-commercialization phase, it is advisable to test the business model with end-users. Although there was considerable interest from users in the Player and the Creator, feedback on various business models and payment options was not collected. Therefore, before preparing the products for the market launch, testing with end-users on the business models would be recommended.

It is also imperative that there is a clear differentiation between the Möbius applications and those already available on the market, (e.g. Amazon Kindle or Apple Books). Möbius outputs should present clear advantages against other similar products. Numerous testers questioned the competitive edge of the Möbius applications and additional testing should be conducted when the products are further developed.

In addition to the number of participants who filled out the surveys, there was a higher number of people who interacted with the piloting staff at the booths where the Möbius outputs were displayed, but these were difficult to record as there were overwhelming numbers of participants at times. In some instances, such as the London Book Fair, the participants were able to scan a QR code to show their interest in the booth, but this was not available at other events, nor used by all participants. Therefore, the total number of people who interacted with the project is difficult to estimate, but it was far greater than the number of people who filled out the surveys. In addition to the surveys collected during events and meetings, the Hotjar platform was used for additional feedback. The questions were directly appearing as the user discovered the Player, the Creator, and the PIT, however the responses collected were not satisfactory as they were mostly uncompleted. For this reason, the answers were not added in the overall number of surveys collected.